

The evolving role of microRNA subtypes 21, 155 and 10b as oncogenes and biomarkers in breast cancer in a decade: A systematic review article.

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Key words

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ABSTRACT

Breast cancer is a malignant disease with a high incidence worldwide in women- and to less extent in men-, thus remains a health burden. miRNA plays a key role in the development and prognosis of breast cancer; as a single miRNA has the ability to regulate multiple gene targets and adversely alter their expression. In this review, we attempt to systematically analyze the rapidly accumulating body of research regarding the role of miRNAs subtypes particularly as oncogenes and biomarkers in breast cancer, and their clinical implications. A total of 11 pertinent articles in the past 10 years were extracted from high-rank reviews, analyzed, and summarized. Amongst many (eight miRNA subtypes), three subtypes (miR21, 155, and 10b) were selected in order to evaluate the validity of their oncogenicity as well as their diagnostic value as biomarkers.

INTRODUCTION

Breast Cancer:

According to the American Society, breast cancer is the most common cancer among women (1). It is a highly heterogeneous complex neoplastic disease with diverse intertumoral and intratumoral non-uniformity that occurs due to abnormal

proliferation of any cells or tissues lining the mammary glands and ducts. Various factors play a role in the development and promotion of breast cancer by changes in the expression of certain genes, amongst which the noncoding RNAs (**miRNAs**) is

worth mentioning (2). Breast cancer can be classified based on their unique phenotype, tumor grade, and molecular characterizations (3). It has been reported that the differential expression of miRNAs in breast cancer, subsequently, an increasing number of studies have suggested that miRNAs are closely associated with BC occurrence and development. Undoubtedly, TNM staging is of great prognostic value; however, considering all the limitations of the currently available prognostic strategies, it is overall recognized that new affordable more accurate methods indicative of molecular characteristics of tumors are needed to achieve personalized treatment. Still, it remains difficult to achieve these goals, because of the absence of refined (sensitive and specific) biomarkers for disease monitoring and for addressing breast cancer on an individual basis (4). MicroRNAs are small single-stranded, non-coding RNA molecules, spanning 19 to 25 nucleotides in length (5). The first discovery of microRNAs (miRNA), *lin-4*, in 1993 by the Ambros and Ruvkun groups in *Caenorhabditis elegans*, (6, 7) has developed the field of molecular biology. miRNAs are transcribed from DNA sequences into primary miRNAs (primiRNAs) and processed into precursor miRNAs (pre-miRNAs) and mature miRNAs. In most cases, miRNAs interact

with the 3' UTR of target mRNAs to interrupt gene expression (6). miRNAs are critical for post-transcriptional gene regulators of various biological functions. They regulate ample cellular and signaling pathways, including cell development and differentiation, cell proliferation, and apoptosis as well as cell migration (7). It is believed that miRNA genes constitute about 1–2% of the known genes in eukaryotes. miRNAs also downregulate gene expression by binding to their specifically target mRNAs 3'-untranslated regions (3'UTRs) leading to either mRNA degradation, translational repression mRNA decay and deadenylation depending on the degree of complementarity with target mRNA sequences. Many genuine researches on miRNA highlighted the involvement of these tiny RNAs in the etiopathogenesis of a variety of human diseases such as neuro-degenerative disorders, diabetes, cardiac hypertrophy, respiratory diseases and have a long history about regulatory relationships between miRNAs and hallmark of cancer, especially breast cancer (2). miRNAs were reported to play many important roles as oncogenes (oncomiRNAs), tumor suppressors and biomarkers. The abnormal expressions of miRNA were also considered to be a potential biomarkers of BC as they are stably detected in tumor tissues and in patients' body fluids, including blood,

plasma, and saliva. miRNAs in body fluids, also called circulating miRNAs, are remarkably stable, packaged into extracellular microparticles or bound with lipoproteins, which protect them from RNase digestions. In this review, we

Biogenesis and Maturation:

Winter *et al* viewed that that the biogenesis of mature miRNA involves series of biological processes. Firstly, the Primary miRNA (pri-miRNA) is transcribed by RNA polymerase II or III in the nucleus, forming an elongated RNA hairpin structure that is subsequently cleaved by Drosha into a small stem-loop structure of ~70 nt, (pre-miRNA) Pre-miRNA is exported from the nucleus into the cytoplasm by exportin-5 and the loop is cleaved after the pre-miRNA is loaded onto Dicer, producing a double-stranded

attempt to scientifically analyze the rapidly accumulating research regarding the emerging role of miRNAs subtypes particularly as oncogenes and biomarkers in breast cancer and their clinical implications (8).

structure of miRNA and antisense miRNA. The latter is typically degraded, whereas the long (~22 nt) mature miRNA strand is incorporated into the miRNA-induced silencing complex (mRISC), leading to mRNA degradation or translational repression. Mature miRNA levels are regulated via binding to ceRNAs such as circular(c) RNAs, pseudogenes, and lncRNAs, which act as a sponge to prevent miRNA binding to target mRNA (9). See (Figure1)

Figure1: Schematic representation of miRNA biogenesis and function. The primary miRNA transcript (pri-miRNA) is transcribed in the nucleus by RNA polymerase II/III, creating an elongated hairpin structure of RNA that is then split into a small stem-loop structure of ~70 nt by Drosha (pre-miRNA). Pre-miRNA is exported by exportin-5 from the nucleus into the cytoplasm and the loop is cleaved after loading the pre-miRNA onto Dicer, creating a double-stranded miRNA and antisense miRNA* structure. The latter is usually degraded, while in the miRNA-induced silencing complex (mRISC), the long (~22 nt) mature miRNA strand is integrated, leading to mRNA degradation or translational repression. Via binding to ceRNAs such as circular (c) RNAs, pseudogenes, and lncRNAs, which function as a sponge, mature miRNA levels are regulated to prevent miRNA binding to target mRNAs.

miRNAs subtypes as oncogenes

The first proof of link between miRNA and cancer derived from studies on B cell chronic Lymphocytic leukemia (CLL), particularly in an attempt to identification of a translocation induced deletion at chromosome 13q14 that frequently detected in CLL (10). The mechanisms of oncomiRNA can be explained by certain number of proteins, some of these proteins are integral component of the RNA induced silencing complex (RISC) that delivers those small RNAs to complementary site within mRNA. miRNAs exert their silencing function usually by interactions with the 3' untranslated region (3' UTR) of target gene through imperfect base pairing. Moreover, miRNAs can function as master gene regulators, impacting a number of cellular pathways important to normal cellular functions as well as cancer development and progression. These alterations culminate in an increased expression of the oncomiR such as miR-21, miR-155 and miR-10b and decreased the tumor suppressor such as Let-7a (2). MiR-10b showed to be upregulated in breast cancer cells, overexpression of miR10b is a target for the transcription factor Twist, which is causes interruption of homeobox D10 (HOXD10) mRNA translation. This leads to increase the expression of Ras homolog gene family member C (RhoC),

which promotes cell invasion and metastasis (11). Similarly, miR-21 plays an important role in many carcinomas, especially breast cancer development and progression. Through increased cell growth in vitro, tumor growth in vivo and inhibits the expression of multi-tumor suppressor proteins such as TIMP3, PDCD4 and tropomyosin 1 (alpha). In addition, it has a major role in invasion and metastasis by targeting multiple anti-metastatic genes. Finally, miR-155 act as oncogene/upregulate factor in breast cancer cells results in suppressing the expression of protein Suppressor of cytokine expression 1 (SOCS1) both in vitro and in vivo, Inhibition of SOCS1 is inversely correlated to pro-tumorigenesis. The miR-155 also represses tumor suppressor for head box O3a expression in breast cancer (12).

miRNAs as Biomarkers

The first study of miRNA measurement in serum was conducted by Lawrie et al. who found that sera levels of miR-21 were associated with relapse-free survival in patients with diffuse large B-cell lymphoma. After that several studies have assessed the potential biomarker use of serum or plasma miRNAs in breast cancer and other different types of cancers, Current challenges in the management of breast cancer include a continuing search

for sensitive minimally invasive markers that can be exploited to detect early neoplastic changes, thus facilitating the detection of breast cancer at an early stage, as well as for monitoring the progress of patients with breast cancer and their response to treatments. Particularly in breast cancer, microRNAs (miRNAs or miRs) have been proposed as promising biomarkers because they can be readily detected in tumor biopsies (non-circulating miRNAs) and can also be identified in blood, plasma, serum, and saliva (circulating miRNAs). Furthermore, circulating miRNAs are bound to lipoproteins such as HDL, are associated with Argonaute 2 (Ago2) protein, or are packaged into exosome-like microparticles, micro-vesicles, and apoptotic bodies. There is also great need for the identification of sensitive, reliable and acceptable markers of response to neoadjuvant and adjuvant therapies (13).

METHOD

A search of PubMed Medline has yielded thousands of papers. The search databases were filtered to identify articles published from 2010 to 2020 using the following search strategy: (microRNA OR miRNA) AND (oncogenes and biomarkers) AND (breast cancer). This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA

guidelines. The Real Time RT-PCR technique was used to identify the miRNA expression level of selected miRNAs. Also, the statistical analyses of miRNA expression profiles of the BC and its stages, were performed using the program SPSS. For the inferential analysis of data, parametric data from T-test non-parametric data from the Mann-Whitney method were used. P value less than 0.05 considered as significant value.

RESULTS

The search strategy retrieved 48 articles. 16 of these articles were duplicates, 6 were not freely available, 2 were not in English, 11 were irrelevant, 2 were not pertinent, 1 was earlier than 2010, and 11 were Eligible. The above mentioned steps concerning the selection of studies are illustrated in detail in (Figure2). Therefore, a total of 11 articles were included in this systematic review and the role of 3 miRNAs molecules as oncogenes & biomarkers is described in (Table1). According to the results, presented in Table1, 81.8% % of published studies have not taken into account of statistical analysis to assess the role of miRNAs in breast cancer, since in (45.4%, of the studies focused on oncogenic miRNAs, and their associated genes on BC, 27.3% their main goal is breast cancer, its classification, and tumor grades, 9.1% of

the articles addressed miRNAs as biomarkers, and the rest studied the processes of miRNAs biogenesis), the remained 18.2% were quantitatively analyzed for the role of miRNAs as oncogenes and biomarkers in breast cancer.

Expression levels of miR-10b were correlated with the breast cancer tumor stages. Generally, the miR-10b expression levels were significantly elevated when the tumor grade is increased (p -value ≤ 0.05). There are no statistically significant changes observed between Stage II and III (p -value ≥ 0.05). Stage III miR-10b expression level is significantly lower than Stage IV (p -value ≤ 0.05). Significant expression level changes were also observed between stages I-II and stages II-IV (p -value ≤ 0.05).

The expression levels of circulating miR-21 in breast cancer patients was significantly higher (p -value ≤ 0.05). There was no

significant difference in the histopathological level of miR-21 expression in patients with breast cancer Grade II and Grade III differentiation, nor Grade III and Grade IV (p -value ≥ 0.05). Also there was no significant difference in the expression of miR-21 according to tumor sizes and breast cancer subtypes. Circulating miR-155 was significantly higher in patients with tumors larger than 5 cm (p -value ≤ 0.05). MiR-155 expression levels were significantly different according to various tumor grades, and clinical stages (p -value ≤ 0.05). No significant difference was observed between any of the studied miRNAs regarding lymph node metastasis. Mir-21 was significantly over-expressed in ER-/PR- cases. Specific miRNAs (miR-10b, miR-21, and miR-155) are associated with tumor metastasis and other clinical characteristics for BC, facilitating identification of individuals who are at risk.

Figure2: Flow diagram represents the methodology of this study and its process.

microRNA subtype	Receptor	Detection method	Role	Target gene	Biological sample, and Tumor stage	P- value	References
miR-10b	ER+,PR+, and Her-	qRT-PCR	Oncogenes, and biomarker	HOXD10	Plasma,	0.5969	(14)
					Tissue	0.3689	(14)
					Stage II, III	0.7400	(15)
					Stage III, IV	0.0040	(15)
miR-21	ER+,PR+, and Her-	qRT-PCR	Oncogenes, and biomarker	MASPIN, TPM1, PDCD4	Plasma,	0.7684	(14)
					Tissue	0.7516	(14)
					Stage II, III	0.0900	(15)
					Stage III, IV	0.5400	(15)
miR-155	ER+,PR+, and Her-	qRT-PCR	Oncogenes, and biomarker	SOCS1	Plasma,	0.8804	(14)
					Tissue	0.2644	(14)
					Stage II, III	0.0078	(15)

Table1: List of role of miRNAs in breast cancer.

DISCUSSION

The expression levels of the miR-21, miR-10b, and miR-155, were derived from patients' tissue (breast cancer biopsy) and plasma samples of BC patients. The results showed a comparable expression pattern among the different samples, with no significant discrepancy. Matamala *et al* represent an exception to this (16). Nevertheless, Svoronos *et al.* concluded a matched expression level of the miRNAs subtypes between breast tumor tissues and serum. In our analysis, miR-21, and miR-155 were significantly over expressed in tumor specimens in comparison to the control (17). In addition, the expression of the miR-21, miR-155, and some other types of miRNAs, was powerfully correlated with the clinicopathologic features of the breast cancer such as tumor grades and sex hormone receptor expression (17, 18). We have also analyzed the results from the previous miRs expression in the plasma to appraise whether there was a correlation between the expression level of the miRs and the various clinic-pathologic features or not. For example, these studies found the expression of the estrogen receptor (ER) and progesterone receptor (PR) is associated with the miR-21 and miR-155. The ER recognized as key factor in motivating the mammary cell proliferation which can lead to up-regulation during the

early stages of tumorigenesis and tumor development (19). Likewise, Al-Khanbashi *et al.* observed the expression patterns of the miRs related with Her2/neu/ER/PR in the breast tumors. In this context, two other independent studies have also shown the expression of miR-21 in the breast cancer patients compared to the healthy ones are increase. In addition, the discover plasma levels of the miR-10b and miR-155 between the breast cancer patients and the healthy, as well, the serum level of the miR-155 in PR+ tumors have exposed a significant dissimilarity in comparison to PR- cases (20). Wang *et al.* (2010) explain the clinicopathological features of the breast tumors such as the histological grades and the sex hormone receptor was connected with the expression of the miR-21 and miR-155 (21). Additionally, we have stratified the patients to look at the relations between the plasma levels of the selected miRs and the stage II/III of the disease based on the TNM staging. In 30 cases of the breast cancer, the miR-21, miR-10b, and miR-155 did prove a significant difference in the staging compromised to the control. Moreover, the expression of miR-155 in the plasma showed a significant variation between stage II and III. Wang et al. (2010) in comparative between the higher malignancy grades and control breast tissues have shown that the miR-21, miR-106a, and miR-155 were significantly up-

regulated in malignancy grades (21). The comparative expression of MiR-155 expression was not changed in the benign tumors but was increased 2 fold and 5 fold in the grade II and III. The miR-21 was not changed in the benign tumors but increased 2 fold in the grade II tumors and 4.5 fold in the grade III tumors. Correspondingly, in contrast, the miR-21, miR-126, miR-155, miR-199a, and miR-335 were highly correlated to ER or PR in both the grades. Additional Studies have also shown that miR-21 can up expression of the oncogene proteins and down expression of the tumor suppressor proteins. Likewise, the miR-21 in the breast tumor tissues has been shown the increase expression to be directly linked to the incidence of the disease, tumor size, and staging.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the expression of the miR-21, miR-155, and miR-10b are downregulated in healthy individuals and upregulated in breast cancer. As well, the results showed a similar expression between the tissue and the plasma samples and noted that there were no significant changes. Furthermore, after operations it found that the chemotherapy and radiotherapy were led to more reduction in the oncomiRs and increase the tumor suppressor genes during treatment can be considered as a good diagnostic tool for the process of perfection and suitable response to the standard treatment. Generally, the difference between the expressions of the miRs could be due to differences in the sample sources, age, stages of tumor cancer, different analytical methods, and/or different platform in the studies. Therefore, it seems that an increasing or decreasing expression of miRs can be related to various reasons.

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